

Le management organisationnel: Quel impact sur l'administration des PME ?

Organizational management: What impact on the administration of SMEs?

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Résumé

Les petites et moyennes entreprises jouent un rôle très important au processus de développement économique d'un pays, elles sont considérées comme un élément crucial de compétition et de rivalité dans tous les domaines et aussi elles constituent l'élément de base des variables socio-économiques.

Bien que le gouvernement attache une grande importance à ces entreprises, il existe encore des problèmes et des obstacles qui entravent leur croissance et leur développement. Parmi ces problèmes on trouve ceux qui concernent le manque d'une excellente gestion et d'une organisation efficace. Et à cause de cela, l'objet de ce travail explore le rôle joué par l'organisation administrative et son impact positif et efficace sur la performance des petites et moyennes entreprises.

Le nombre des variables étudiées étant important et nous considérons cette recherche comme préalable nécessaire nous permettant de formuler un certain nombre d'hypothèses concernant l'organisation administrative par rapport aux déterminants de la performance de l'entreprise. Concernant l'approche de collecte des données, nous avons opté pour la méthode quantitative via une enquête sur un échantillon composé de 256 entreprises de la région du nord du Maroc.

Mots clés : PME ; Organisation ; Management ; Administration ; Performance.

Abstract

Small and medium-sized enterprises play a very important role in the process of economic development of a country, they are considered as a crucial element of competition and rivalry in all fields and also they constitute the basic element of socio-economic variables.

Although the government attaches great importance to these companies, there are still problems and obstacles that hinder their growth and development. Among these problems are those relating to the lack of excellent management and efficient organization. And because of this, the object of this work explores the role played by administrative organization and its positive and effective impact on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises.

The number of variables studied being large, we opted for one-dimensional analysis. We consider this research as a necessary prerequisite allowing us to formulate a certain number of hypotheses concerning the administrative organization in relation to the determinants of the performance of the company. Concerning the data collection approach, we opted for the quantitative method via a survey on a sample made up of 256 companies from the northern region of Morocco.

Keywords: SMEs; Organization; Management; Administration; Performance.

Introduction

Known for its specificities in terms of financing, organization and in particular management mode, small and medium-sized enterprises constitute a major player in the industrial sphere of several countries, even developing countries going through a strong period of transformation of their economic environment. Recent statistics show that SMEs represent more than 90% of companies in the world and contribute to the creation of 50% to 60% of jobs. In the USA, the same rate is 70%, in France, 81% and in the European Union, the rate of contribution to job creation for these companies is 81%. This shows the importance of small and medium-sized businesses to many economies around the world. Morocco is a country that has been undergoing radical transformations in its economic environment for nearly thirty (30) years, therefore, it will be necessary to go back to the end of the eighties (80) to detect the beginnings of a favourable policy, the development of SMEs, particularly private ones. Systems for creation, supervision and support have been put in place, which has freed up entrepreneurial energies and generated an economic dynamic characterized by the rapid and significant development of SMEs / SMIs in a framework that is still undergoing transformation⁽¹⁾.

Certainly, business creation is a fundamental economic and social issue, particularly in the context of the crisis and reforms affecting our national economy. However, past experiences show that the act of business creation, an essential and tangible element of economic dynamics, remains insignificant and insufficient if the business created does not display a certain resistance and certain viability. The survival rate of businesses in Morocco is only around 40% five years after creation. This shows that not even half of the newly created companies are present after five years of existence. The process of their growth and development in turn appears problematic because of the obstacles most often encountered.

The Tangier-Tetouan, Al Hoceima region, which has an industrial fabric represented by VSB (44%) and *SMEs* (42%), despite the importance of the creation of firms observed annually on rates survival, is only about 30% of companies five years after creation. The scarcity of

¹ This dynamic was remarkable especially during the period from 1995 to 2000 when an annual growth rate of 22% was recorded. Further expansion was confirmed after the adoption of the new investment code of 2001, which has enabled SMEs to represent more than 75% of companies in recent years.

companies that have defied these figures arouses great curiosity and deserves the researcher's interest.

The reasons for the choice of the subject are due to a set of motives:

- The large and growing number of SMEs in different countries whether developed or not;
- International organizations are concerned about the status of these institutions and the support provided by certain international financial bodies;
- Shed light on the field of management and organizations of SMEs;
- The subject is consistent with the specialization which is considered to be one of the subjects that fall at the heart of economics and management of an organization;
- SMEs have become one of the most important solutions offered to university graduates to avoid the unemployment crisis.

This research aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Collect what has been written on the subject of an administrative organization trying to apply it to SMEs;
- Highlight the role of the administrative organization function in the performance of SMEs;
- Know the reality and the nature of the organization prevailing in SMEs;
- The evaluation of the organization variable as a qualitative variable requires special treatment.

The present research contributes to answering the following research questions:

- What is the reality of administrative organization in SMEs?
- What is the impact of the administrative organization of SMEs on their profitability?
- What is the impact of the administrative organization of SMEs on its internal operations?
- What is the impact of the administrative organization on the learning and growth of an SME?

1. Literature Review

The question of performance has been addressed since Antiquity. We only find that Adam Smith (Smith. A) was interested in it. Its effectiveness is related to the extent of the division of labour, but the excess of this division turned the worker into a simple machine, which is

reflected negatively on performance. As for Max Weber² (M.), he saw it in terms of normality and stereotypes, except Frederick Taylor (Taylor F)³ saw that specialization and division of labour alone are not enough to improve performance. , but rather it is necessary to monitor the performance of the worker. While doing the work to improve performance and increase productivity by studying time and motion.

Due to the call for improvement working conditions, wages and the emergence of ideas from the School of Human Relations, Elton Mayo (E) focused on the factors Social, humanitarian and material working conditions to improve performance and increase productivity, such as the creation of informal organizations. While Henry Fayol (H.) believes that effective performance can only be achieved by ensuring sound management based on supporting science. The institution must control the management of its resources, particularly human resources and with the emergence of new concepts such as the expansion of work. In addition, job enrichment has changed theory into performance, from performance to be rewarded to performance is a reward, and workers have become able to watch the satisfaction and fulfilment of their needs, not only through work but rather by high performance.

In the literature, there is a multiplicity of definitions of the notion "Administrative organization". What we have noticed in several authors like P. Drucker⁴ the organization is "A cognitive function and a work of managers to carry out actions and tasks". As for Taylor Frederik, the organization is: "Knowing exactly what you want, then making sure people do it in the best and cheapest way possible." As for "A system of integrated mental activities", management is defined in terms of leadership and systems theory as "Objectives and plans, which aim at continuous interaction with the external environment and its variables and adapt to it to achieve the objectives».

Based on the previous definitions of the pioneers of ancient and modern thought, an organization can be defined as conscious humanitarian work based on a set of activities that allow the establishment of institutions and projects and their functioning. The administrative organization ensures that its objectives are achieved efficiently and effectively, taking into account internal and external influences on the working environment.

² In his Book "economy and society" published in 1922.

³ In his Book "The principals of scientific management" published in 1911.

⁴ In his Book "The practice of management " published in 1954.

Table N ° 1: Measuring indications for successful Organizational management

Variables	Items
Profitability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An optimal time investment. ▪ Optimal use of available resources. ▪ Increase the degree of efficiency to achieve the objective. ▪ Improved negotiating power of the institution. ▪ Help create excellence for the institution.
Internal operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Vitality and attention to official time. ▪ Encourage bottom-up communication (bottom to top). ▪ Achieve a high degree of control and thereby reduce the gaps. ▪ Improve the quality and efficiency of internal operations. ▪ Provide a model of human relations dominated by understanding, participation and exceptional performance. ▪ Facilitate the flow of information and promptly. ▪ Achieve good coordination between individuals and departments.
Learning and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enable the organization to seize opportunities and avoid threats. ▪ Improve the superior perception of subordinates. ▪ Increase autonomy in the performance of work. ▪ Growing responsibility for work. ▪ Increase the desire to work. ▪ Meet the needs of workers and increase their sense of their importance in the institution. ▪ Provide an appropriate working environment. ▪ Achieve a good level of satisfaction and belonging to the workers. ▪ Development of innovation and creativity. ▪ Solve problems more precisely and quickly. ▪ Encouragement to make suggestions to improve the work. ▪ Increase the institution's capacity to attract and retain qualified workers. ▪ Reduce labour turnover and increase worker stability. ▪ Create an atmosphere of competition and challenge within the institution. ▪ Increase the possibility of cooperation with other institutions.

Source: Aharouay.S &all

2. Research Framework

The main objective of our work is the analysis of the factors that have contributed to the survival of small and medium-sized enterprises and the conditions for their sustainability; will focus on two essential points. The presentation of the methodological benchmarks of the survey carried out in the field and that of the key concepts (sustainability, survival and SMEs) will be the subject of the first point. The second, on the other hand, will be entirely devoted to

the presentation of the data and results of the survey as well as their analysis, The interest shown by the public authorities in the promotion of SMEs in Morocco on the one hand, and the phenomena of disappearance child development of some SMEs as well as that of the survival and sustainability of a few, on the other hand, have led us to pose the following problem:

To what extent can administrative organization influence the performance of SMEs?

To highlight our work and to better respond to this problem, we carried out a field survey with a sample of 20 SMEs, 95% of which are private family-run and most of which are beyond the start-up stage.

Figure 1: The hypotheses and the research model

On the basis of the reasoning pursued, we formulated the hypotheses of our research as follows:

Hypothesis 1: The administrative organization has a positive impact on the performance of SMEs. This hypothesis is divided into three sub-hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1.1: The administrative organization has a positive impact on the profitability of SMEs.

Hypothesis 1.2: The administrative organization has a positive impact on the internal operations of SMEs.

Hypothesis 1.3: The administrative organization has a positive impact on the learning and growth of SMEs.

3. Methodology

The field study is considered as a projection of the theoretical aspect of the research, and this study cannot be carried out without constructing for it a methodological framework allowing the identification and organization of the information that must be obtained to get the search results. To do this, this research will be divided according to the following requirements:

3.1.Descriptive and analytical approach

To collect data and information on the phenomenon covered by the study and describe the results achieved, analysed and interpreted. To collect the basic information of the current study by relying on the survey (questionnaire), which is the tool most used by researchers, to collect the data of the study, each according to its interest and its discretion, and summarize the summary, and summarize the information Institutional components and components of both concepts and some of the forms that have been carried out in some previous studies and research.

3.2.Data collection method

The investigative technique that we have chosen is the questionnaire because it seemed to us the most appropriate in order to have sufficient information. The data were personally administered to 256 companies in the northern region of Morocco during the period from November 2019 to March 2020. We have chosen the non-probability sampling method, more precisely, of convenience; this choice is justified by the absence of a sampling frame.

3.3.The choice of measurement scales for the different variables of the study

Note that all variables are measured using one or more measurement scales. Starting from theory, the variables in our study are measured by items that are cited in the literature review. The scale chosen for this research was a scale of attitudes and opinions. This being the case, we have chosen to apply the Likert scale for each of these variables which is an interval scale making it possible to measure the attitude of an individual who is asked to express the intensity of his approval or of his disapproval of a statement by choosing one of the degrees offered.

4. Results and Discussion

To analyse the data collected and verify the research hypotheses, we first reported to principal component analysis (PCA) and secondly, we used CFAs to judge the validity of our measurements. The relationships of the independent variables and the absorptive capacity are evaluated using the method of structural equations.

The principal component analysis is used to study the relationships between the different elements of each variable and to examine the factor structure of the set of items. For the set of measurements used, the measurement of the sampling precision is satisfactory. The data can therefore be subject to factor analysis and form a sufficiently coherent whole. Concerning Table 1, we can conclude that the quality of representation is good for all the items which form the constructs, which indicates that they measure the factor concerned fairly well. The reliability test indicates Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.7.

Table 1: Summary table of the psychometric qualities of the measurement scales

Scale	KMO	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha	Rho of Joreskog	VME
Administrative Organization	0,643	66,156%	0,740	0,831	0,711
Profitability	0,815	83,563%	0,930	0,752	0,753
Internal Operations	0,733	76,347%	0,845	0,714	0,695
Learning & Growth	0,657	66,121%	0,742	0,826	0,738
SME Performance	0,725	82,485%	0,891	0,684	0,826

Source: Aharouay.S &all

We checked the conditions necessary for the application of the method of structural equations (the condition of normality, multi-normality, and sample size). Then, we evaluated the goodness of fit of the global measurement model which has greatly improved after the introduction of certain modifications and presents globally satisfactory indices as indicated in Table 2 and this by referring to the thresholds usually used by the items cited in the literature review.

Table 2: Results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the measurement model

CHI2/dl	GFI	AGFI	CFI	TLI	NFI	RMSEA	RMR
1.164	0,935	0,906	0.991	0.988	0.941	0.028	0.047

Source: Aharouay.S &all

To validate our hypotheses, we were led to use, on the one hand, multivariate analyzes of the second generation, more precisely structural equations. The use of structural equations is justified above all by the fact of studying the causal relationships between several explanatory variables and several variables to be explained, moreover, these different variables are latent.

The results of our hypotheses are presented in Table 3. Based on these results, we can state that the assumptions and have been verified insofar as the p is significant in the supposed sense of the relationship. While the relationship has been invalidated since the p threshold recommended by the literature ($p < 0.05$) is not respected. Therefore the research hypothesis is partially confirmed.

Table 3: Validation of regression links

Hypotheses	Links	Standardized regression coefficients	CR	p
H _{1.1}	OA → Profitability of SMEs	,186	1.568	,060
H _{1.2}	OA → Internal Operations	,177	1,435	,078
H _{1.3}	OA → Learning & Growth	,429	2,017	,000

Source: Aharouay.S &all

Conclusion

The small and medium-sized enterprise sector, and more than before, has become of particular importance, due to the unique advantages it has and also the resulting economic impact contributing very effectively to the achievement of development of economic and social goals.

There is a global consensus to adopt the programming of small and medium-sized enterprises as the most effective means of combating poverty and unemployment, and therefore the

Moroccan authorities at all levels pay particular attention to this sensitive sector which can positively influence and/or negative economic growth depending on the strategies adopted to improve them.

However, it should be noted that whatever the positive role of small and medium-sized enterprises in development does not negate or neglect the problems and difficulties that these institutions suffer from, in addition to the great challenges that these institutions will face. In light of the current global economic changes represented in globalization and join the World Trade Organization, regional and international economic blocks and step up trade liberalization processes and the investment and the resulting increased competition locally and abroad.

Meeting these challenges requires small and medium-sized enterprises to have a separate administrative organization based on Scientific and methodological foundations, taking into account all the factors that affect it, and supporting its nature with its positive aspects, and including It achieves the difficult combination of the three sides of the Triangle of Excellence (innovation and creativity, cost, customer satisfaction).

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